

Checklist for documentation analysis of tools

1. Installation instructions:

- **Complete:** The instructions are detailed and cover all necessary steps for installation.
- **Medium:** The instructions are useful but may lack some details.
- **Insufficient:** The instructions are very scarce or nonexistent.

2. Installation methods:

- **Complete:** Offers multiple installation methods (local, web, Google Colab, etc.).
- **Medium:** Provides some installation methods but not all possible options.
- **Insufficient:** Offers very few or no alternative installation methods.

3. Code examples:

- **Complete:** Provides clear and sufficient code examples to understand the use of the tool.
- **Medium:** Provides some examples, but they may not be enough to fully understand the tool.
- **Insufficient:** Does not provide code examples, or the examples are very limited.

4. Documentation of functions and methods:

- **Complete:** The documentation covers all functions and methods in detail.
- **Medium:** The documentation covers the main functions and methods but not all of them.
- **Insufficient:** The documentation is very scarce or nonexistent.

5. Update history:

- **Complete:** A detailed history of all updates is maintained.
- **Medium:** The update history is available but not detailed.
- **Insufficient:** No update history is available.

Herramienta	Puntuación	Installation instructions			Installation methods			Code examples			Documentation of functions and methods			Update history		
		Complete	Medium	Insufficient	Complete	Medium	Insufficient	Complete	Medium	Insufficient	Complete	Medium	Insufficient	Complete	Medium	Insufficient
Arena	Insufficient			✓		✓			✓			✓				✓
ExplAIner	Insufficient			✓			✓		✓			✓				✓
ModelStudio	Medium		✓			✓			✓			✓		✓		
What-if tool	Medium	✓			✓			✓				✓		✓		
AIX360	Complete	✓			✓			✓			✓			✓		
ALIBI	Complete	✓			✓			✓			✓			✓		
An eXplainability toolbox for machine learning	Medium		✓			✓				✓		✓		✓		
CARLA	Medium		✓			✓			✓		✓					✓
CEML	Medium	✓				✓		✓				✓	✓			✓
DALEX	Complete	✓			✓			✓			✓			✓		
ExplainerDashboard	Complete	✓			✓				✓			✓		✓		
Intel XAI tools	Medium		✓			✓			✓		✓			✓		
InterpretML	Complete	✓			✓			✓			✓			✓		
OmniXAI	Complete	✓			✓			✓				✓		✓		
SHAPASH	Medium	✓				✓			✓			✓	✓			